

Research Article

Drivers and spatial pattern of post-socialist suburban development: A case of a second-tier Ukrainian city

Oleksiy Gnatiuk¹

¹ Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Kyiv, Ukraine

Corresponding author: Oleksiy Gnatiuk (oleksii.gnatiuk@knu.ua)

Abstract

This study explores the drivers (explanatory factors) and spatial patterns of suburban development in Vinnytsia, a second-tier Ukrainian city, within the broader context of post-socialist urban transformation. The objective of the paper is to identify the drivers of suburban development of Vinnytsia as a second-tier Ukrainian city at the level of individual settlements and to uncover the general spatial patterns of its suburban area. Drawing on spatial features of suburbanisation including population change, housing modernisation, real estate market activity, and construction permits, the research reveals a distinct centre–periphery structure of the suburban area, asymmetrically distributed along the southwest–northeast axis. The suburban area comprises three quasi-concentric zones, each exhibiting varying levels and forms of suburban development. The first zone, directly adjacent to the city, is dominated by classical western-type suburbanisation, involving the influx of affluent residents and the emergence of low-rise and multi-storey housing. The second zone, stretching 15–20 km from the city centre, is characterised by housing modernisation rather than new construction, with commercial activity concentrated near major highways. The third zone, up to 30 km away, shows only partial transformation, mainly through the renovation of existing homes, which may be equally referred to both suburban and peri-urban development. Logistic regression confirms proximity to the central city as the most influential factor across all indicators, while landscape features and access to highways also contribute significantly. The research identifies asymmetries rooted in both natural landscape preferences and the spatial configuration of the city itself. Notably, administrative reforms have failed to align governance boundaries with functional suburban integration. The study concludes that suburbanisation in Vinnytsia reflects hybrid dynamics of post-socialist development, merging unregulated urban expansion with spontaneous and policy-driven modernisation. The findings offer insights for spatial planning in second-tier cities, advocating for more integrated approaches to suburban and peri-urban governance.

Key words: Factors, post-socialist city, suburbanisation, Vinnytsia

Academic editor: Chad Staddon

Received: 26 April 2025

Accepted: 21 August 2025

Published: 01 October 2025

Citation: Gnatiuk O, Klymenko A (2025) Drivers and spatial pattern of post-socialist suburban development: A case of a second-tier Ukrainian city. *Journal of the Bulgarian Geographical Society* 53: 87–118. <https://doi.org/10.3897/jbgs.e157082>

Copyright: © Oleksiy Gnatiuk & Anna Klymenko
This is an open access article distributed under terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License ([Attribution 4.0 International – CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)).

1. Introduction

The suburban area is a dynamic environment where urban and rural areas interact, leading to a fundamental transformation of traditional settlement systems, changes in the social structure of the population, the emergence of unique

land-use patterns, and landscape transformations. Researching the drivers (explanatory factors) of suburban development helps identify patterns in these processes, which is crucial for effective planning and management of urban and regional development. Understanding suburban development drivers at the level of individual settlements allows for identifying areas with the highest growth potential and those at risk of socio-economic stagnation, predicting the load on transport, social, and environmental infrastructure, preventing chaotic construction, irrational land use, and urban conflicts (McGregor et al. 2005; Ravetz et al. 2013; Kubeš and Nováček 2019). Ultimately, this contributes to the balanced development of the city and its suburban area, as well as of specific parts of the latter.

In post-socialist countries, suburban development typically differs significantly from the western model, represented first of all by the typical US or Canadian suburbs (Beauregard 2006; Kubeš and Nováček 2019), due to differences in socio-economic and institutional conditions during the post-socialist era (Borén and Gentile 2007; Leetmaa and Tammaru 2007; Zakutynska and Slyvka 2016; Lozynskyi 2022). The legacy of Soviet planning also plays a significant role. During the socialist period, cities developed under strictly regulated schemes that did not account for market-driven migration mechanisms and did not allow classical suburbanisation processes to unfold fully. Instead, summer residences (so-called “dachi”) served as a socialist surrogate for classic suburbia (Leetmaa et al. 2012). However, with the collapse of socialism, control over spatial development weakened considerably, leading to chaotic suburban construction, the destruction of green spaces, agricultural land, and valuable natural landscapes, as well as an increasing imbalance between housing development and service sector expansion (Kubeš and Nováček 2019; Lozynskyi 2019; Hardi et al. 2020). This also resulted in rising commuter migration and, consequently, increased pressure on transport infrastructure, along with growing social segregation between affluent suburbanites and the less affluent local long-term residents (Gnatiuk et al. 2021). Unregulated suburban development can lead to a range of social and environmental problems, making this issue particularly critical for post-socialist countries. In turn, successful management of suburban development requires an understanding of the factors and spatial patterns of suburban expansion in post-socialist cities.

Understanding differences in suburban development at the settlement level is crucial because each suburban settlement has its own unique characteristics, including the level of transport connectivity with the central city, access to urban infrastructure, natural features (terrain, presence of water bodies, forests), socio-economic composition of the population, economic characteristics, local heritage, and identity (Kok and Kovács 1999; Mantey and Sudra 2019; Gnatiuk et al. 2021; Lozynskyi 2022). This is particularly important in the context of a general trend toward decentralisation and the increasing role of local self-government in democratic countries, where many spatial development decisions are made at the local level. Thus, research focusing on a local level helps develop targeted development policies that consider the specific needs and potential of particular areas. Studying the explanatory factors of suburban development at the settlement level is essential for ensuring the balanced growth of urban regions. For post-socialist cities, which have undergone significant changes in governance structures, economy, and demographics, such

research not only helps explain current trends but also allows for forecasting future development scenarios while minimising the risks of uncontrolled urban sprawl (Slaev and Kovachev 2014; Werner et al. 2022; Cochechi and Petrişor 2023).

The vast majority of literature on suburban development in post-socialist countries focuses on large metropolises, with only a few publications exploring the peculiarities of second-tier cities (Matlovič and Sedláková 2007; Gnatiuk 2016; Zakutynska and Slyvka 2016; Repaská et al. 2017; Kubeš and Nováček 2019; Hardi et al. 2020; Gnatiuk et al. 2021; Hardi 2022; Kubeš and Ouředníček 2022; Ilieva et al. 2023). Moreover, despite a significant shift in the past decade, Ukraine remains on the periphery of knowledge production regarding even post-socialist suburban development (Kryczka et al. 2025). By focusing on the second-tier city of Vinnytsia, Ukraine, we aim to address this gap and provide new insights into suburban development from a global urban periphery. The objective of this study is to identify the factors influencing suburban development in Vinnytsia as a second-tier Ukrainian city at the level of individual settlements, as well as to uncover the general spatial pattern of its suburban area. A spatial pattern of suburban area refers here to the geographic distribution and configuration of suburban growth, including the location, density, and structure of residential areas, transport networks, and land use types in relation to the central city.

Traditionally, the development of the suburban area is closely associated with the process of suburbanisation. In its classical sense, suburbanisation refers to the movement of predominantly affluent city dwellers to the suburbs, driven by environmental considerations – to escape the disadvantages of urban life and seek a higher-quality and more family-oriented lifestyle in greener, more private, and socially exclusive settings. As a result, classical western-style suburbs are typically low-rise residential areas that remain highly dependent on the central city for employment, leading to increased commuting (Hirt 2007). Additionally, suburbanisation refers to the stage of urban region development when the population of suburban area is growing faster than that of the city in absolute or relative numbers (Osada 2003; Sýkora and Posová 2011; Kryczka et al. 2025).

However, the observed forms of city-to-hinterland interaction worldwide are not limited to classical western-style suburbanisation. Instead, suburbanisation is just one of several processes or types of suburban development (Ford 1999; Hirt 2007; Ouředníček 2007).

In particular, four types of peri-urban growth have been identified based on the origin of migrants, their relationship to the metropolitan region, their motivation, housing quality and accessibility (Ford 1999; Fisher 2003): (1) suburbanisation – migration from the metropolitan centre to the nearest suburbs; (2) counter-urbanisation – migration from the metropolitan centre to more distant suburban zone; (3) population retention – maintaining population levels within the suburban area; and (4) centrifugal migration – from the suburbs back to the metropolitan centre.

Depending on the social profile, origin, employment and main motivation of migrants, the following processes changing the face of suburban area are distinguished (Hirt 2007): (1) western-type suburbanisation – the relocation of affluent households from the metropolitan centre to rural areas; (2) urban ruralisation, or de-urbanisation – the movement of low-income populations from the metropol-

itan centre to the peri-urban area; and (3) rural urbanisation – the movement of low-income populations from the rural hinterland to the metropolitan centre.

Developing the framework of the differentiated suburban development, Ouředníček (2007) identified seven migration processes based on motivation, connection to the central city, housing quality, and the influence of previous and new places of residence: (1) from the metropolitan centre to newly built housing (suburbanisation); (2) from the metropolitan centre to already existing old housing; (3) from the metropolitan centre to nursing homes for the elderly; (4) from the metropolitan centre to a second home (seasonal suburbanisation); (5) from the metropolitan centre to distant locations (de-urbanisation); (6) within the suburban zone (tangential migration); (7) from other parts of the country and abroad (long-distance migration).

Lozynskyi (2022) explicitly warns that suburban villages in Ukraine should not be referred to as “suburbs” or “suburbia” since only a portion of them resembles traditional American suburbs. He suggests that the term “suburbs” should be applied only to those parts of suburban villages or city outskirts that exhibit characteristics typical of American suburbs.

Alongside the concept of suburban development, there is a related but distinct term – peri-urban development. The latter refers to the structural transformation of rural areas under the influence of the city, resulting in the blurring of the boundary between urban and rural spaces, the formation of a mixed urban-rural landscape, and the interweaving of urban and rural functions. Peri-urban area is generally defined as an urban-rural transition belt that experiences a substantial impact from the city in social, economic, and environmental aspects, making it significantly different from adjacent rural areas beyond the city’s direct influence (Iaquinta and Drescher 2002; McGregor et al. 2005; Avram 2009; Piorr et al. 2011; Ravetz et al. 2013; Gottero et al. 2023; Zborowski et al. 2023). Existing theoretical models of peri-urban areas describe gradual centre-periphery transition from the central city to the rural hinterland: the rural-urban continuum model (Waugh 2000) distinguishes suburban area, urban shadow and rural area, while the spatial morphology model (Thuo 2013) outlines such basic structural elements of the urban region as inner and outer urban fringes, urban shadow, and rural hinterland. Cities are seen as centres of innovation diffusion and poles of growth (Perroux 1955; Friedmann 1972), capable of significantly transforming the suburban area even in the absence of direct population migration to or from it. Given the multiplicity and diversity of forms of suburban development and approaches to define this mere concept (Forsyth 2012), in this research we often cannot clearly distinguish the features and results of pure suburbanisation from those of peri-urbanisation, and thus the terms “peri-urban area” and “peri-urban development” are often used in the article, albeit the main focus is retained on suburbanisation.

The specific development trajectories of entire suburban areas and their individual parts are highly variable and resist universal systematisation, requiring a deep understanding of regional and local contexts.

Firstly, the development of suburban areas is influenced by the broader social, economic, cultural, and political-institutional context (Borén and Gentile 2007; Leetmaa and Tammaru 2007; Leetmaa et al. 2009; Brade et al. 2010; Slaev and Kovachev 2014; Lozynskyi 2022). The factors and spatial patterns of suburban development depend on the combination and interplay of the pro-

cesses (e.g. suburbanisation, de-urbanisation, counter-urbanisation) occurring within a particular urban region, reflecting motivations of migrants to and from suburban area.

Secondly, the transformation processes within suburban areas vary significantly depending on the size of the central city. More detailed theoretical explanation of this pattern has been proposed within the framework of a differential urbanisation theory (Geyer and Kontuly 1993; Kontuly and Geyer 2003). It has been demonstrated, including based on the Ukrainian material (Mezentsev and Havryliuk 2015; Gnatiuk 2017; Havryliuk 2021), that largest cities are faster entering the subsequent stages of urban evolution, and suburbanisation processes are more intensive, although there are numerous deviations from the general rule. The patterns of migrations (centrifugal vs. centripetal) and motifs of migrants may also differ depending on the size of a central city/urban region in the same country (Mezentsev et al. 2019, 2020).

Thirdly, the vast majority of suburban areas exhibit a clear centre-periphery structure with respect to the central city, subdividing into several zones that differ in the presence, intensity, and proportion of various phenomena such as residential, commercial, and industrial suburbanisation, as well as processes like suburbanisation, counter-urbanisation, etc. (Leetmaa and Tammaru 2007; Pidgrushnyi et al. 2020; Sikorski and Szmytkie 2021). This structure tends to be more extensive, pronounced, and polycentric (with additional economic growth poles as edge cities, etc.) in large metropolitan areas (Sýkora and Ouředníček 2007; Marcińczak 2012; Tanaś 2013; Pidgrushnyi et al. 2023) and more compact, less differentiated, and monocentric in second- and third-tier cities (Matlovič and Sedláková 2007; Zakutynska and Slyvka 2016; Kubeš and Nováček 2019; Ilieva et al. 2023). The influence of local factors can introduce significant asymmetry in the development of particular sectors of the suburban area. Therefore, the presence of a general visible asymmetry (Gnatiuk 2016) or a sectoral structure aligned with the routing of major transport arteries (Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017; Kubeš and Nováček 2019; Gierczak-Korzeniowska 2020; Ubarevičienė and Burneika 2020; Dudek-Mańkowska et al. 2024; Jurkowski et al. 2024) is a fairly widespread phenomenon.

Fourthly, the intensity and nature of suburban development can vary significantly between different parts of the suburban area and specific suburban settlements. Research on suburban development in the Prague metropolitan area demonstrates variations in spatial patterns, the intensity of spatial processes, and the social and economic status of new suburbanites (Ouředníček 2007). Mezentsev (2017) identifies five types of suburban spaces in Ukraine, differing in their surrounding environment, the nature of changes, housing types, and lifestyles: rural settlements affected by suburbanisation, new cottage towns, former seasonal “dacha” settlements transformed into permanent residences, growing Soviet-era satellite towns, and areas of intra-urban suburbanisation. Mantey and Sudra (2019), based on the Warsaw Metropolitan Region setting, elaborated a typology of suburbs based on six criteria: (1) the level of neighbourhood (spatial scale), (2) the time when the neighbourhood was erected, (3) spatial interaction with the nearest town/city, (4) the prevailing type of investment, (5) street layout, and (6) access to the city centre by public transport. More or less similar typologies of suburban settlements have been proposed by different authors for different contexts (Zębik 2011; Repaská et al. 2017).

Fifthly, extreme heterogeneity of suburban built environments and lifestyle forms is observed (Walks 2013; Dymitrow and Stenseke 2016; Phelps 2017; Keil 2018), as well as coexistence of different built forms and lifestyles within a single suburban settlement (Mezentsev et al. 2019; Gnatiuk et al. 2021; Lozynskyi 2022), and, at times, even within a single street (Provotar and Melnychuk 2025).

Given the aforementioned diversity of suburban areas, we can identify certain general groups of explanatory factors that either promote or hinder the development of suburban settlements. Despite the global trend toward increasing functional autonomy and independence of suburban areas (Golubchikov et al. 2010; Harris 2010; Pidgrushnyi et al. 2020), a significant—and in some cases critical—dependence of everyday life in the suburbia on the central city persists. With this in mind, two factors are typically decisive: the distance to the central city and the quality of transportation connections (Wolny and Żróbek 2017; Bogusz et al. 2024; Dudek-Mańkowska et al. 2024). For affluent suburbanites, a key advantage is the availability of fast and high-quality road connections, while for poorer population greater importance is placed on suburban rail and bus services, as well as the extension of urban public transport routes into the suburban area. Proximity to the central city is also important in terms of locating large retail and logistics centres in the suburban area – they must be easily accessible for urban residents as well, which makes locations at the very edge of the city, within reach of public transport, the most favourable (Ronse et al. 2015; Peiffer-Smadja and Torre 2018; Sikorski and Szmytkie 2021). In recent years, alongside transportation connectivity, the quality of mobile communication and internet access has also become increasingly important.

The status and population size of a suburban settlement also matter (Kubeš and Ouředníček 2022). On the one hand, the largest suburban settlements – particularly satellite towns and urban-type settlements – typically have more developed economies (and therefore more job opportunities) and better social infrastructure, making them more attractive to migrants (Bogusz et al. 2024). In addition, due to the hierarchical nature of spatial innovation diffusion (Hägerstrand 1967), the development of commercial infrastructure in the largest and most prominent settlements occurs more rapidly (Ronse et al. 2015; Peiffer-Smadja and Torre 2018; Pidgrushnyi et al. 2020; Sikorski and Szmytkie 2021; Kazakov et al. 2024). On the other hand, from the perspective of affluent suburbanites seeking proximity to nature and social exclusivity, relatively small villages may be more attractive (Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017).

Important factors that attract potential residents of classical western-style suburbia include environmentally favourable living conditions and picturesque landscapes, such as the presence of rivers, lakes, and forested areas (Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017; Ubarevičienė and Burneika 2020; Bogusz et al. 2024). At the same time, it should be noted that environmental factors and proximity to “unpleasant” or hazardous facilities do not always act as limiting factors. For instance, cottage towns in the suburban area of Kyiv—the Ukrainian capital—are being built in the direction of the Chernobyl Exclusion Zone, near landfills for solid and construction waste, and close to the Trypillia Thermal Power Plant (Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017). Natural conditions also matter as factors that either create more convenient conditions for construction (flat terrain, low groundwater levels, stable soils, access to water resources), or, on the contrary, hinder development (rugged terrain, dense forests, swamp-

iness, flood or landslide risks, etc.) (Marushchynets 2020; Ubarevičienė and Burneika 2020). This applies not only to residential development but especially to industrial and commercial construction. Therefore, the same natural conditions may have opposite effects on the development dynamics of a suburban settlement depending on the local context.

Among other drivers, the image and reputation of a particular settlement must be mentioned. Settlements with a well-developed local identity and landmarks may experience higher development rates. Low land and property prices also contribute to the development of suburban areas (Bogusz et al. 2024). However, intensive suburban growth typically leads to a surge in prices, meaning that often prices should be considered not as a driver but rather as a feature of suburban development. In some cases, the factor of ethnicity matters too (Ubarevičienė et al. 2015; Šveda et al. 2016). Finally, legal and administrative settings play an important role, including local authorities and their policies regarding territorial development (Kok and Kovács 1999). In particular, this concerns the development strategy of the suburban community (e.g., whether to integrate into the central city or to remain a separate community), spatial planning and permitting policies (such as whether multi-story, industrial, or commercial construction is allowed), and investment policy.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Case study area

The city of Vinnytsia, a regional centre in the south-west of Ukraine with a population of ca. 370000, has already been the subject of suburbanisation studies in Ukraine (Gnatiuk 2016, 2017; Gnatiuk et al. 2021). Over the past decades, Vinnytsia has been among the Ukrainian cities demonstrating pronounced population growth in the peri-urban area, while the population of the city itself has stagnated or even declined (Gnatiuk 2017). This trend indicates that the city and its urban region have entered the suburbanisation stage of the urban development lifecycle (for different approaches to the definitions of the suburbanisation stage of urban development see Osada (2003), Sýkora and Posová (2011) and Havryliuk et al. (2021)).

Research on housing modernisation based on remote sensing data (Gnatiuk 2016) suggests that the suburban development of Vinnytsia is influenced by several key factors: the aesthetic qualities of landscapes, the configuration of major transport arteries, differences in the functional profiles of various parts of the central city, and geographical position relative to other adjacent cities. The area influenced by the central city was found to have an average radius of 25 km, albeit with distinct spatial asymmetry. In particular, the highest rates of suburban growth were observed in the south-western and western sectors.

Two factors may be potentially important for shaping this uneven suburban development around Vinnytsia. The first of them is a pattern of natural landscapes (Fig. 1). The landscapes to the west and south-west of Vinnytsia exhibit higher aesthetic appeal due to more dissected terrain, greater forest coverage, and picturesque granite outcrops in river valleys, in contrast to the predominantly flat and heavily cultivated landscapes to the north-east and east of the city. Thus, the landscapes in the western sector may be more attractive

Figure 1. The study setting. Elaborated by the authors based on Google Maps (2024), Population Statistic of Eastern Europe (2024), and Denysyk GI et al. (2008).

to suburbanites. Simultaneously, plain terrain and more fertile soils may favour the industrial and agricultural development eastward of the city. The second explanatory factor may be spatial structure of the central city (Fig. 2). Vinnytsia's historical core is located in its western (right-bank) part and contains the majority of the city's educational and cultural institutions. The largest residential neighbourhoods are concentrated in the western and south-western peripheries of the city. Residential and commercial-service developments, oriented toward the end-user, directly border the suburban area in this part of the city. In contrast, the north-eastern and eastern outskirts of Vinnytsia represent an almost continuous belt of industrial and warehouse zones, which form an undesirable neighbouring environment for potential suburban residents and hinder access to commercial infrastructure – for example, the nearest shopping malls in the inner city. This may hinder residential suburbanisation, however, it does not necessarily impede industrial and, to a lesser extent, service-oriented suburban development (cf. Ubarevičienė and Burneika 2020).

More recent research (Gnatiuk et al. 2021) focusing on Ahronomichne, a village on the urban fringe of Vinnytsia (marked with the letter A in Fig. 1), has revealed a dominant western-type pattern of peri-urban development. Specifically, the majority of newcomers are former urban residents, most of whom relocated from the central city. These newcomers tend to be more affluent than

Figure 2. Spatial structure of Vinnytsia: main morphological and functional areas. Elaborated by the authors based on the Vinnytsia Master Plan (Vinnytsia City Council 2021).

long-term residents and have higher social status. Their primary motivations for moving to suburbia include a quieter living environment and better health conditions, aligning with the broader concept of urban escape. Furthermore, most newcomers reside in newly constructed housing. However, some suburbanites in Ahronomichne reported mixed motivation—urban escape combined with lower housing costs—indicating that the stream of migrants to suburbia is not homogeneous: wealthy migrants are accompanied by individuals with relatively lower incomes (Gnatiuk et al. 2021). Of course, Ahronomichne is only one rural settlement in the suburban zone of Vinnytsia, so the conclusions drawn from it cannot be unconditionally extended to other parts within the suburban or, more so, peri-urban area. Nevertheless, it provides some general understanding of the suburban development on the city’s urban fringe. Therefore, the suburban development of Vinnytsia should be classified as suburbanisation (migration from the central city to the nearest suburban belt) (Ford 1999; Fisher 2003), western-type suburbanisation (relocation of wealthy households from the central city to the countryside) (Hirt 2007), and centrifugal migration from the central city to the suburban area, predominantly to the newly-built housing (Ouředníček 2007).

2.2. Methodology

Previous studies on the suburban development of second-tier Ukrainian cities (Gnatiuk 2016; Zakutynska and Slyvka 2016; Malchykova and Pylypenko 2017; Gnatiuk et al. 2021) suggest the following key considerations: (1) the area of analysis should extend approximately 25–30 km from the central city, (2) primary attention should be given to drivers of suburban development related to the urban escape motivation of affluent residents, such as the aesthetics of the natural and built environment and the absence of undesirable or potentially hazardous facilities, while (3) the high dependence of suburbanites on the central city should not be overlooked, particularly in terms of proximity to the city and access to well-developed transportation infrastructure, such as major roads or reliable suburban train connections.

Based on these considerations, data on potential predictors (explanatory factors, drivers) and indicators (features, visible manifestations) of suburban development were collected for all settlements within a 30 km radius of Vinnytsia (Fig. 1). All predictors and indicators were measured or calculated for each settlement. In this study, a settlement was defined, in accordance with current Ukrainian legislation, as “a compactly populated place of human residence that has emerged as a result of historical traditions, economic and other activities, has a stable population, its own name, and a distinct territory with legally established boundaries” (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine 2024). In total, 158 settlements entered the study, including two cities (Hnivan, Kalynivka), eight townships (Brailiv, Desna, Lityn, Stryzhavka, Sutysky, Turbiv, Tyvriv, Voronovytisia), and 148 villages (Fig. 1).

The potential drivers (predictors) of suburban development, described in Table 1 and partially shown in Fig. 1, were selected based on the assumption that suburbanites primarily originate from the central city, their economic status is likely to be relatively high, and their primary motivation for relocating to the suburban area is environmental – that is, driven by urban escape.

Given the lack of reliable official statistical data at the level of individual settlements, a combination of four different indicators (features, manifestations) of suburban development has been used. While none of them individually covers the entire post-socialist period or represents all aspects of suburban development, together they provide a more comprehensive and consistent picture. Two threshold values were defined for each indicator: “weak” and “strong”. The “weak” threshold value was chosen as the value that separates the background values typical of rural areas from those of settlements that are evidently influenced by the central city. In turn, the “strong” threshold value was selected to distinguish the group of settlements exhibiting the most intense (and atypical) manifestations of suburban development. A certain degree of subjectivity in the researchers’ choice is possible here, however it could not significantly affect the results of the analysis.

Indicator 1: Annual population growth rate (%) from 1989 to 2001. This indicator, calculated using consistent official datasets from the population censuses of 1989 and 2001 (Population Statistic of Eastern Europe 2024), provides direct insight into the demographic dynamics of suburban settlements during the first decade after the collapse of the USSR. Threshold values were defined as 0.00 (“strong”) and -0.25 (“soft”). The key limitations of this dataset are:

Table 1. Potential drivers (predictors) of suburban development of Vinnytsia.

Driver (predictor)	Rationale / Hypothesis
Distance to the central city centre: < 10 km; 10–20 km; > 20 km (ref. > 20 km)	The influence of the central city is expected to weaken with increasing distance from it
Distance to the main motorway: ≤ 4 km; > 4 km (ref. > 4 km)	Affluent suburbanites are expected to use private cars to reach the central city, while poorer individuals may rely on suburban bus routes
Distance to the nearest suburban train station: ≤ 4 km; > 4 km (ref. > 4 km)	Less affluent people may use suburban trains to reach their homes or summer residences ("dachi") in the suburban area
Forest coverage (2 km vicinity of the settlement): < 10%; 10–20%; > 20% (ref. < 10%)	Forested areas may be more attractive as residential locations, especially for affluent suburbanites
Water coverage (2 km vicinity of the settlement): < 0.2%; 0.2–0.5%; > 0.5% (ref. < 0.2%)	The presence of water bodies may serve as an additional attraction for suburbanites, particularly for wealthier individuals
Landscape: Type 1: undulating loess plain upland; gray and dark gray podzolized soils; oak-hornbeam forests; Type 2: Loess and sandy old terraces; gray and dark gray podzolized soils; pine and pine-oak forests; Type 3: Slightly undulating loess plain upland; deep chernozems; rare oak-hornbeam forests (ref. type 3)	Landscapes of types 1 and 2 are considered more attractive (picturesque) for suburbanites than those of type 3 due to their undulating relief and richer forest vegetation
Undesired object / facility (solid waste dump, aeration plant, airport, quarry, ammunition depot, penal institution): no objects in 5 km; at least 1 object in 5 km (ref. no objects in 5 km)	Affluent suburbanites may avoid settling near such undesirable sites due to unpleasant odours, noise pollution, the risk of hazardous substances entering the environment, higher crime rates, or explosion risks. However, for less affluent individuals, these concerns may be less significant; on the contrary, such facilities may provide employment opportunities for them
Population (in 1989, near the supposed starting point of suburban development): < 500; 500–1000; > 1000 (ref. > 1000)	Living in smaller settlements is expected to offer closer proximity to the natural environment, making it more attractive to affluent suburbanites. At the same time, larger settlements typically provide better social infrastructure and more employment opportunities, which may be more important for less well-off individuals

(1) it does not account for officially unregistered residents, including internally displaced persons due to the Russian invasion or those living in Soviet-era summer houses, and (2) it does not cover more than two decades (2002–2024) of post-socialist suburban development. Unfortunately, reliable data on the population at the level of individual settlements after 2001—the year of the last national census—are not available in the country. The existing data refer only to the pre-2020 administrative districts, which significantly reduces the spatial resolution. Nevertheless, within the boundaries of the former Vinnytsia district, excluding the city of Vinnytsia (the configuration is not shown on the map), the population increased from 76.4 thousand in 2010 to 81.2 thousand in 2020, which stands in sharp contrast to the population decline observed in other districts of Vinnytsia region (Main Department of Statistics in Vinnytsia Region 2025). Also, to some extent, the following indicator allows to capture population changes indirectly over a broader time span.

Indicator 2: Share of new/modernised residential units (individual apartments in residential blocks, townhouses or cottages and individual detached houses) in 2024 per settlement. To identify new or modernised residential units, Google Maps satellite imagery was analysed (Google Maps 2024), supplemented by field observations when necessary. The satellite imagery was examined for: a) newly developed land plots; b) modern roofing materials on detached houses that have been available on the Ukrainian market only since the 2000s (e.g., coloured metal, ceramic, and bitumen tiles). These materials, under favourable

lighting conditions, are easily distinguishable from traditional Soviet-era roofing materials (e.g., asbestos slate or galvanised metal sheets) (Gnatiuk 2016; Lozynskyi 2019); c) other modern features not typical of the Soviet era, such as ceramic tile paths, open water pools in yards, and solar panels. Threshold values were defined as 9% (“strong”) and 5% (“soft”). This indicator offers several advantages: (1) it covers the entire post-socialist period, and (2) it captures a broader range of suburban development beyond purely demographic growth, such as housing renovations and the construction or refurbishment of summer residences that may not have registered residents (Leetmaa et al. 2012). However, there are also limitations. First, under unfavourable lighting conditions, the accuracy of visual identification of modern materials and structures decreases. Although field observations were used to verify doubtful cases, some errors may still persist. Second, modernised apartments in Soviet-era residential blocks are not captured by this method. However, this limitation is mitigated by the fact that Soviet-era residential blocks are relatively rare in the studied area, particularly in rural settlements, which constitute the majority of suburban settlements under analysis. To summarise, this indicator basically allows tracing population dynamics in the suburban area of Vinnytsia, but simultaneously covers the process of existing housing stock modernisation; it reflects both manifestations of suburbanisation and peri-urbanisation.

Indicator 3: Number of real estate market advertisements available in February 2025 on the real estate online portal DOM.RIA per 1000 residents (DOM.RIA 2025). The activity of the real estate market serves as a valuable indicator of suburban development intensity, as it directly reflects migration patterns, territorial expansion, and changes in the spatial structure of the suburban area. In particular, real estate demand indicates interest in suburban living and drives the development of transport, social, and commercial infrastructure, further attracting new residents. Threshold values were defined as 25 (“strong”) and 5 (“soft”). The primary limitations of this dataset are: (1) the narrow timeframe, which may not fully capture long-term trends, and (2) the ongoing full-scale Russian–Ukrainian war (since 2022), which could distort real estate market dynamics.

Indicator 4: Number of Issued Planning Conditions and Restrictions per 1000 residents from 2017 to 2024 (Official Register of Planning Conditions and Restrictions 2025). In Ukraine, since 2017, Urban Planning Conditions and Restrictions (hereafter referred to as Construction Permits) are official regulatory documents outlining planning and architectural requirements for new construction or major reconstruction projects. Registers of issued Construction Permits are publicly available in the official state database. This indicator was used to assess economic activity in suburban settlements, including residential, commercial, and industrial suburbanisation. Threshold values were defined as 2 (“strong”) and 0 (“soft”). Alongside with the relative numbers, the absolute numbers of the issued Construction Permits together with the functional structure of the respective objects are provided for better understanding. The limitations of this indicator include: (1) the narrow time frame for which the data is available (2017–2024) meaning it does not account for the first 25 years of post-socialist transformation, and (2) potential distortions due to war-related economic and investment fluctuations.

A series of maps was created for the four specified indicators of suburban development, illustrating their spatial patterns in relation to potential predic-

tors. An integrated map of suburban development intensity was constructed using the multivariate average of all four indicators. Probably, this is not the best way to evaluate the integral level of suburban development, because the indicators are mutually correlated, and the exact weights of them are unknown; nevertheless, this approach allowed taking into account a variety of suburban development dimensions including population dynamics, housing stock construction and modernisation, economic activity and real estate market.

Additionally, for each indicator (separately for both 'strong' and 'soft' criteria), binary logistic regression models were built using SPSS software to identify statistically significant predictors of suburban development at the level of individual settlements. Logistic regression is a statistical method used to model the relationship between one or more independent variables and a binary dependent variable. It estimates the odds that a given input belongs to a particular category by applying the logistic (sigmoid) function to a linear combination of the input variables (Boateng and Abaye 2019). Logistic regression was chosen over linear regression for three reasons: (1) to minimise the impact of random inaccuracies in the input data; (2) because some parameters, such as landscape type, are represented by nominal scales; (3) because logistic regression results are easier to interpret for applied urban and regional development purposes. The authors acknowledge that the constructed models may be unstable due to the small number of suburban settlements in certain categories violating the optimal events-per-variable ratio (Peduzzi et al. 1996; Vittinghoff and McCulloch 2007). This is especially relevant for models with 'strong' criteria. Therefore, the results of the logistic regression are interpreted with caution, taking into account the entire set of constructed models and in triangulation with cartographic visualizations of suburban development indicators.

3. Results

The first indicator of suburban development—population growth between 1989 and 2001 (Fig. 3A)—reveals a clear centre-periphery gradient. The innermost zone comprises settlements directly adjacent to the administrative boundary of Vinnytsia, where almost exclusively positive demographic trends were recorded, with some villages exceeding an annual growth rate of 5%. The second, more distant zone, demonstrates more favourable demographic dynamics compared to the background trends observed in the broader hinterland. It exhibits a distinct sectoral structure, with clusters of growing settlements aligned along major highways extending westward, south-westward, northward, and south-eastward. The outer boundary of this zone lies approximately 10–15 km from the city boundary.

The centre-periphery structure is further shaped by a general asymmetry along the southwest–northeast axis, observable within each of the identified zones. In the first zone, for instance, suburban settlements located to the west and south-west of the city recorded an average annual population increase exceeding 1%, whereas in other directions the growth rate did not surpass 1%, and some settlements bordering the city even experienced population decline. In the second zone, the stimulating effect of highway corridors remains evident up to 15 km from Vinnytsia in the west, south-west, and partially in the north.

In contrast, this influence diminishes to approximately 10 km in the south-east and just 5 km in the north-east.

Regarding the size and administrative status of suburban settlements, the highest population growth was recorded in relatively small rural villages, whereas urban-type settlements and small towns did not display any distinct comparative advantage.

Taking into account the timing of the intensification of residential suburbanisation processes in Ukraine – the beginning of 2000s (Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017), as well as the predominantly classical centrifugal nature of migration combined with the primarily environmental motivations of suburban movers (Gnatiuk et al. 2021), the spatial pattern under consideration can be interpreted as a snapshot of the early stage of post-socialist residential suburbanisation around Vinnytsia. At this stage, suburban settlers were primarily interested in the most accessible rural settlements located directly adjacent to the city, as well as those situated along key highways. Notably, the observed spatial pattern reflects primarily the influence of migration rather than natural population change, although separate migration data are not available. This indicator confirms that the demographic dynamics of settlements directly adjacent to Vinnytsia differed from the background trends even before 2001. This may reflect both the actual beginning of residential suburbanisation and smaller demographic losses in suburban villages compared to the general depopulation of rural areas in the region as an effect of peri-urbanisation.

The second indicator—the share of new or modernised residential units (Fig. 3B)—reveals a substantially larger size of suburban area. This can be attributed, firstly, to the broader temporal coverage and, secondly, to the fact that this criterion allows for the identification of the indirect, modernising influence of the central city on the suburban area, which is not necessarily accompanied by population migration. Nevertheless, a centre-periphery structure is evident in this case as well. The first zone includes settlements directly adjacent to Vinnytsia, characterised by very high proportions of new or modernised housing, in some cases exceeding 100%. This is essentially the result of the construction of new suburbs, where the number of newly built residential units surpasses the number of housing units that existed prior to the onset of active suburbanisation. In the second zone, the indicator ranges between 5% and 50%, gradually declining with increasing distance from the central city. While the stimulating effect of radial highways remains visible, it is less decisive here than in the case of the previous indicator. Instead, an elevated share of new or modernised residential units is observed along the course of the main local river – the Southern Buh. On average, the outer boundary of the second zone lies approximately 15–20 km from the city boundary.

The overall spatial asymmetry of suburban development is particularly evident in this case as well. Within the inner zone (urban fringe), all settlements where the share of new or modernised housing exceeds 100% are located to the west of Vinnytsia, whereas in the eastern and south-eastern sectors this figure does not exceed 5% – effectively rendering the zone nearly nonexistent in those directions. Similarly, the outer boundary of the second zone extends nearly 25 km from the city boundary to the south-west, while it reaches only 5–10 km to the north-east.

Regarding the size and status of suburban settlements, rural localities exhibit such a marked advantage over townships and small towns that it cannot be

Figure 3. Indicators (features) of suburban development around Vinnytsia. Elaborated by the authors. The size of the circles reflects the population of the settlements in 2001. **A** Population growth rate (%), 1989–2001 (Population Statistic of Eastern Europe 2024) **B** Share of new / modernised residential units (%) 2024 (Google Maps 2024; personal field observations) **C** Realty advertisements (February 2025) per 1000 residents (2001) (DOM.RIA 2025) **D** Construction permits per 1000 residents (2001), 2017–2024 (Official Register of Planning Conditions and Restrictions 2025).

fully attributed to methodological limitations (such as the underestimation of modernised housing units in multi-storey apartment buildings).

Given its extensive chronological coverage, this indicator appears to most comprehensively reflect changes in the housing sector of Vinnytsia's suburban area, capturing both the direct process of suburbanisation and the modernising influence of the central city. In particular, residents of suburban villages tend to engage more actively in the modernisation of their homes due to increased income opportunities from employment in the city, improved physical access to goods and services markets in Vinnytsia, and emulation of the lifestyles and housing aesthetics of more affluent suburban migrants (Gnatiuk et al. 2021).

The spatial pattern reflected by the third indicator represents a snapshot of the real estate market in the suburban area of Vinnytsia as of 2024 (Fig. 3C). Again, we observe the leading development of the urban fringe, a more distant zone characterised by a gradual decline in real estate market activity to background hinterland levels, and a general asymmetry along the southwest–north-east axis, which is evident within both zones. However, the similarity between the patterns is not complete. In particular, a significant number of settlements with a relatively high share of new or modernised housing exhibit very low real estate market activity. This discrepancy may be attributed to differences in the temporal coverage of the two indicators, as well as to instances of housing modernisation undertaken by suburban residents without property transactions – a phenomenon more typical of the more remote suburban zone.

The analysis of the fourth indicator—the number of issued construction permits (Fig. 3D)—reveals a somewhat different spatial pattern. Firstly, the contrast between the urban fringe and the more remote suburban zone is less pronounced. Secondly, while the overall spatial asymmetry persists, its nature is different: within the urban fringe, the most intensive development traditionally occurs in the western direction, whereas in the more distant suburban zone, it is observed toward the east and south-east. Overall, the area of evident urban influence extends approximately 15–20 km beyond the city's outer boundary. Thirdly, the size and status of the settlement appear to matter: towns and urban-type settlements stand out with higher numbers of issued construction permits, both within the zone of clear urban influence and beyond it, at distances exceeding 20 km from the city boundary. This discrepancy can be explained by the fact that the previous indicators referred exclusively to the residential sector, whereas construction permits cover various sectors of development. In this case, it may be supposed the role of small towns located 20–25 km from Vinnytsia as secondary centres of modernisation.

A deeper understanding of the situation can be gained by analysing the functional affiliation of the facilities under construction or reconstruction (Fig. 4). Permits for the construction and reconstruction of housing were issued in a limited number of suburban settlements, primarily those located near the border of Vinnytsia. These are the areas where individual apartment buildings, entire residential complexes, as well as large townhouses and gated cottage communities are being developed. The same settlements recorded the highest number of permits in the commercial real estate sector, indicating that commercial suburbanisation around Vinnytsia largely follows residential development and is oriented toward serving the suburban population (cf. Matlovič and Sedláková 2007; Pidgrushnyi et al. 2020, 2023). At the same time, commercial real estate

permits were also issued in other settlements that are not undergoing mass housing development. These are mainly settlements located near major highways, where commercial facilities cater not only to the local population but also to transient flows of clients, including those from the central city. In particular, auto service stations, logistics centres, and large chain supermarkets are thriving in these areas (cf. Dębińska and Pałubska 2021). It is also evident that residential suburbanisation has triggered the development of the social infrastructure in the suburban zone, especially in the areas closest to the central city. The typical spatial asymmetry of issued construction permits across the analysed sectors is again observed, with the western and south-western sectors developing ahead of the north-eastern and eastern sectors. By contrast, the eastern sector is more active in the implementation of infrastructure projects – a likely explanation being that part of this sector belongs to the Vinnytsia urban territorial community, which, since its establishment in 2020, has carried out significant municipal investments in the infrastructure development of suburban villages.

The question that has remained unaddressed thus far concerns the reason for the overall spatial asymmetry observed in Vinnytsia's suburban area. This asymmetry follows a distinct and recurrent pattern across various indicators. Based on the range of identified empirical facts, both differences in the natural landscapes to the west and the east of the city and the spatial structure of the central city itself may contribute to the observed pattern.

Before drawing final conclusions on the factors influencing suburban development in Vinnytsia, it makes sense to examine the results of the logistic regression analysis (Tables 2, 3). The most important factor, by far outweighing all others in magnitude, is proximity to the central city. In particular, a distance of less than 10 km from the centre of Vinnytsia (reference category: >20 km) increases the likelihood of a settlement experiencing very intensive suburban development by between 14 times (construction permits) and 1430 times (realty advertisements); a distance within the 10–20 km range increases these odds by between 6 times (population growth) and 43 times (realty advertisements). A distance to a major highway of less than 4 km proved to be a statistically significant predictor only for real estate advertisements (both strong and soft criteria, with odds ratios of 13.3 and 4.9, respectively), and for construction permits (only for the soft criterion, with an odds ratio of 2.7).

In several models, landscape type also has a statistically significant impact. For instance, settlements located within landscape type 1 were significantly more likely to fall into the category of those with the highest population growth (odds ratio: 5.6) and the largest share of new or modernised residential units (odds ratio: 11.2). Similarly, settlements within landscape type 2 had higher odds of experiencing strong population growth (odds ratio: 3.9) and the highest activity of realty market (odds ratio: 2.4). However, the forest coverage factor, initially hypothesised as a predictor of more intensive suburban development, turned out to be largely insignificant; in one of the models (forest coverage >20%, construction permits, soft criterion), it was even a statistically significant predictor of weaker suburban development (odds ratio: 0.3). The water coverage factor was also mostly statistically insignificant, except in one model (water coverage 0.2–0.5%, new/modernised residential units, soft criterion),

Figure 4. Absolute numbers of issued construction permits and functional types of (re) constructed objects. Elaborated by the authors based on Official Register of Planning Conditions and Restrictions (2025).

where a positive relationship between water coverage and suburban development was detected.

Regarding the size and status of the settlement, it was found that the smallest villages (population < 500) were significantly more likely to be among those with the highest share of new or modernised residential units. At the same time, small settlements (population in between of 500 and 1000) were less likely to have large number of construction permits issued. For factors such as proximity to suburban railway stations and proximity to undesirable facilities, no statistically significant influence on suburban development indicators was detected.

Thus, the most important driver determining the intensity of settlement development in the suburban area of Vinnytsia during the post-socialist period is proximity to the central city. At the same time, proximity to major highways, landscape type, and settlement size also play a significant role. Considering that landscape type appears as a statistically significant predictor only for certain indicators of suburban development, it is likely that the internal spatial

structure of the central city (as previously discussed) also exerts an influence. At the same time, no statistically significant effects were identified for forest coverage, water coverage, proximity to suburban railway stations, or proximity to undesirable facilities.

Based on the multivariate average of all four indicators (features of suburban development), the suburban area of Vinnytsia exhibits a centre-periphery structure consisting of three quasi-concentric zones, asymmetrically distributed around the central city, with clear hints of sectoral star-shaped pattern related to the main river and motorways (Fig. 4). Drawing on the findings of this study, including field observations, and previous studies (Mezentsev et al. 2019; Gnatiuk et al. 2021), these zones can be characterised together as follows.

Table 2. Binary logistic regression results (odds ratios): predictors for ‘very intense’ suburban development.

Independent variables (covariates)	Population growth (1989-2001), % > 0.00	New/modernised residential units (2024), %, > 9	Construction permits per 1000 residents (2017–2024), > 2	Realty advertisements (February 2025) per 1000 residents (2001), > 25
Distance to central city centre: 10–20 km (ref. > 20 km)	5.825*	33.843***	7.146**	42.770***
Distance to central city centre: < 10 km (ref. > 20 km)	36.987***	774.700***	14.220**	1430.736***
Distance to main motorway: < 4 km (ref. > 4 km)	1.845	2.632	3.380	13.345*
Distance to suburban train station: < 4 km (ref. > 4 km)	0.895	1.547	0.801	0.786
Forest coverage: 10–20% (ref. < 10%)	0.502	2.753	0.804	1.384
Forest coverage: > 20% (ref. < 10%)	1.144	2.022	0.941	1.659
Water coverage: 0.2–0.5% (ref. < 0.2%)	0.611	1.033	0.657	0.656
Water coverage: > 0.5% (ref. < 0.2%)	0.689	3.598	1.030	3.590
Landscape: type 1 (ref. type 3)	5.590*	11.282*	0.603	0.215
Landscape: type 2 (ref. type 3)	3.870*	4.431	0.563	2.444*
Undesired object: at least 1 object in 5 km (ref. no objects)	2.734	2.309	2.057	2.617
Population (1989): 500–1000 (ref. > 1000)	0.660	1.522	0.700	0.967
Population (1989): < 500 (ref. > 1000)	0.541	9.692*	0.879	2.117
Constant	0.010	0.000	0.029	0.000
Overall correct predictions, %	89.2	89.9	83.5	93.0
Hosmer-Lemeshow Test (Sig.)	0.046	0.927	0.266	0.948
Nagelkerke R Square	0.327	0.604	0.323	0.723

Note: odds coef. = Exp(B); * p < 0.1; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001.

Source: Calculations by the authors.

The first zone includes settlements directly adjacent to Vinnytsia and is characterised by the highest intensity of suburban development. The primary driver of growth here is classical western-type suburbanisation. Large clusters of new suburbs are emerging in this area, coexisting with older parts of villages and townships, which are also undergoing substantial modernisation. This is the only zone where multi-storey residential construction with apartment blocks is present. In some locations, the new housing merges seamlessly with that of the city, making this area increasingly resemble a natural extension of the urban fabric. Commercial suburbanisation is oriented, on the one hand, towards meet-

Table 3. Binary logistic regression results (odds ratios): predictors for ‘moderately intense’ suburban development.

Independent variables (covariates)	Population growth (1989–2001), % > - 0.25	New/modernised residential units (2024), %, > 5	Construction permits per 1000 residents (2017–2024), > 0	Realty advertisements (February 2025) per 1000 residents (2001), > 5
Distance to central city centre: 10–20 km (ref. > 20 km)	3.737*	12.338***	4.346**	41.191***
Distance to central city centre: < 10 km (ref. > 20 km)	8.612**	189.357***	3.349	269.738***
Distance to main motorway: < 4 km (ref. > 4 km)	1.723	1.566	2.731*	4.904*
Distance to suburban train station: < 4 km (ref. > 4 km)	1.156	1.120	1.151	1.015
Forest coverage: 10–20% (ref. < 10%)	0.704	1.410	0.591	1.285
Forest coverage: > 20% (ref. < 10%)	0.684	1.463	0.263*	3.288
Water coverage: 0.2–0.5% (ref. < 0.2%)	1.784	3.695*	0.532	0.533
Water coverage: > 0.5% (ref. < 0.2%)	1.055	1.684	0.976	2.148
Landscape: type 1 (ref. type 3)	2.319	4.198*	1.014	0.450
Landscape: type 2 (ref. type 3)	1.952	6.614**	0.523	1.042
Undesired object: at least 1 object in 5 km (ref. no objects)	2.591	0.529	1.236	0.956
Population (1989): 500–1000 (ref. > 1000)	0.710	1.588	0.172**	0.938
Population (1989): < 500 (ref. > 1000)	0.381	4.415*	0.082***	1.630
Constant	0.006	0.015	0.947	0.120
Overall correct predictions, %	82.9	82.3	81.6	88.6
Hosmer-Lemeshow Test (Sig.)	0.758	0.625	0.483	0.921
Nagelkerke R Square	0.261	0.514	0.467	0.683

Note: odds coef. = Exp(B); * p < 0.1; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001.

Source: Calculations by the authors.

ing the needs of Vinnytsia residents (e.g., large retail chains), and on the other hand, follows residential suburbanisation by responding to the demands of the new suburban population. While the lifestyle of residents in this zone is mostly suburban, it increasingly acquires urban characteristics (cf. Gnatiuk et al. 2021).

The second zone includes settlements located approximately 15–20 km from Vinnytsia’s centre in south-western direction, narrowing to 5–10 km in the north-eastern direction. Western-type suburbanisation is also present here, though large-scale clusters of new suburban development are rare. A more significant role is played by the modernisation of existing housing stock – either by newcomers or by long-term residents. Commercial activity is weak and generally consistent with typical rural development patterns in the region, with the exception of settlements along major highways, where commercial services are more oriented toward serving transit traffic. The everyday life of residents in this zone likely combines elements of both suburban and rural lifestyles.

The third zone extends up to approximately 30 km from the city centre in the south-western direction and narrows to 15–20 km in the north-eastern direction. The influence of the central city is substantially weaker here, centrifugal migration plays only a minor role, and continuous suburban development clusters are largely absent. Nonetheless, levels of suburban development—particularly in terms of modernising existing housing—remain above the background

Figure 5. Spatial structure of Vinnytsia’s suburban area.

levels observed in the wider hinterland. The prevailing lifestyle in this zone is rural, with isolated suburban elements. Commercial suburbanisation has not reached this zone up to the moment.

4. Discussion

The spatial extent of post-socialist suburbanisation in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) mostly depends on the population size of the city (Kubeš and Nováček 2019). This study confirms the previous estimate of the suburban zone of Vinnytsia as extending approximately 15–20 km from the city boundary (cf. Gnatiuk 2016). At the same time, the settlements that can be classified as suburbs according to the criteria presented in the literature (Kubeš and Nováček 2019), are located within 5–10 km from the city boundary. When compared with other CEE cities (Matlovič and Sedláková 2007; Czaková 2009; Halás et al. 2012; Šveda et al. 2016; Wolny and Żróbek 2017; Kubeš and Ouředníček 2022; Zborowski et al. 2023), it becomes evident that the suburban area of Vinnytsia (with a population of around 400000) corresponds in spatial extent to that of CEE cities with populations of approximately 100000. This relative underdevelopment of Vinnytsia suburban area – at least in terms of residential and commercial suburbanisation – can be attributed to the later onset and lower intensity of suburbanisation processes in Ukraine compared to other CEE countries (Mezentsev 2017; Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017). Furthermore, the spatial extent of Vinnytsia suburban area is significantly smaller than that of Ukraine's capital city, a major metropolitan centre (Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017; Pidgrushnyi et al. 2023). At the same time, it is slightly larger than the suburban zone of Ivano–Frankivsk, a second-tier city in western Ukraine with a population of approximately 250000 (Zakutynska and Slyvka 2016). This is consistent with Vinnytsia's larger population and its evident transition to the suburbanisation stage, in contrast to Ivano–Frankivsk, where the central city has continued to grow at a faster pace than its suburban area (Gnatiuk 2017).

The suburban area of Vinnytsia exhibits a relatively simple quasi-concentric structure that aligns well, in terms of suburban development intensity, dominant processes, and prevailing lifestyles, with existing theoretical models of peri-urban areas. For instance, within the rural-urban continuum model (Waugh 2000) the first concentric zone can be interpreted as suburban, the second as the urban shadow, and the third as a rural area with a modest, yet non-negligible, urban influence. According to the spatial morphology model of urban regions (Thuo 2013), the first zone corresponds to the outer urban fringe, the second to the urban shadow, and the third to the rural hinterland. According to Zborowski et al. (2023), the first concentric zone is a zone of suburbanization, taking a form of typical urban sprawl, while the second and third zones form a zone of peri-urbanization/commuting. Clear parallels can be drawn with the centre-periphery spatial structure observed in other cities of similar rank both in Ukraine (Zakutynska and Slyvka 2016) and beyond (Kubeš and Nováček 2019; Ilieva et al. 2023). At the same time, as in many other cases, the concentric structure of Vinnytsia suburban area is distorted by sectoral asymmetry. Unlike larger metropolitan areas, where this asymmetry is typically driven by the orientation of radial road and rail corridors (Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017; Podawca et al. 2019; Kubeš and Ouředníček 2022; Pidgrushnyi et al. 2023; Dudek-Mańkowska

et al. 2024; Jurkowski et al. 2024), in the case of Vinnytsia, it can be primarily attributed to differences in natural landscapes and the specific spatial configuration of the central city itself (cf. Šveda et al. 2016; Zakutynska and Slyvka 2016; Ubarevičienė and Burneika 2020).

The spatial asymmetry of suburban development observed in the case of Vinnytsia poses significant challenges for the integrated development of the city and its suburban area. Following the administrative-territorial reform of 2020, the least developed suburban settlements located to the east and north-east of Vinnytsia opted not to establish independent territorial communities, but instead chose to join the Vinnytsia urban territorial community. Lacking strong sources of revenue for their local budgets, these settlements prioritised the benefits of cooperation with the city, particularly in terms of budgetary investments in infrastructure development. In contrast, settlements to the west, north, and south of Vinnytsia—characterised by more intensive suburbanisation and stronger economic capacity—chose to establish their own separate territorial communities, thereby retaining control over their local resources. As a result, a paradoxical and inefficient situation emerged in terms of city-suburb governance: the suburban settlements most closely integrated with the city (some parts of them are effectively transforming into de-facto urban neighbourhoods) were excluded from the boundaries of the urban territorial community. This is partly the result of the shortcomings of the 2015–2020 administrative-territorial reform and the absence of an effective mechanism for intermunicipal cooperation within urban agglomerations in Ukraine (Udovychenko et al. 2017; Pavlov et al. 2024). New challenges also arise in the context of the Russian–Ukrainian war. In 2023, a modular settlement for internally displaced persons was established in the urban-type settlement of Voronovytsia, located south-east of Vinnytsia. It can be assumed that the choice of location for the modular settlement was driven by the “lower prestige” of this sector of the suburban area. As a result, the socio-spatial contrast between different sectors of the suburban area is further exacerbating, while the residents of the modular settlement turn out to be maximally isolated in spatial terms from the main benefits of urban life compared to being located in another part of the suburban area (cf. Havryliuk 2024).

The identified drivers shaping the development of the suburban area of Vinnytsia align with the western-type suburbanisation process: affluent suburbanites, motivated by the pursuit of more comfortable and higher-quality living conditions in closer proximity to nature, relocate from the central city while maintaining strong ties to it. Depending on their financial capacities, these suburbanites choose more expensive housing in detached houses or townhouses, opt for more affordable apartments in multi-storey buildings, or invest in the modernisation of older homesteads. The availability of social infrastructure and local employment opportunities in the suburban area is not a decisive factor for such migrants due to their regular connection with the central city. This situation mirrors that of post-socialist second- and third-tier cities (Matlovič and Sedláková 2007; Kubeš and Nováček 2019; Ilieva et al. 2023), but contrasts with post-socialist metropolises, where economic development and social infrastructure are among the key drivers of suburban growth (Brade et al. 2010; Bogusz et al. 2024; Dudek-Mańkowska et al. 2024; Kazakov et al. 2024). A similar contrast exists with Kyiv, where clusters of western-style classical suburbs

coexist with high-rise suburban developments inhabited by various categories of in-migrants, including those from other regions of the country, who are in search of cheaper housing and a more affordable lifestyle in proximity to the capital (Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017; Mezentsev et al. 2019, 2020). Since affluent Ukrainians primarily rely on private vehicles rather than the largely uncomfortable suburban rail services, and given the relatively limited spatial extent of the suburban area, suburban rail connectivity proves insignificant for the development of suburban areas in second-tier cities – unlike in first-tier cities. At the same time, as in the case of Kyiv (Mezentsev and Mezentseva 2017), the presence of unpleasant or undesirable facilities does not appear to hinder the suburban development of Vinnytsia. Considering the environmentally driven motivations of classical suburbanites, this phenomenon deserves further in-depth investigation.

Although the process of suburbanisation—primarily residential and, to a lesser extent, commercial—plays a key role in transforming the suburban area of Vinnytsia, the city's influence on its periphery extends beyond suburbanisation alone (cf. Zborowski et al. 2023). We also observe both spontaneous and intentional modernisation effects of the central city on suburban settlements. The spontaneous, unregulated impact—outside the direct control of state or municipal authorities—manifests itself through the modernisation of housing by local residents, their utilisation of the advantages of proximity to a large city, partial adaptation of everyday practices to urban lifestyles, and changes in land use patterns (cf. Gnatiuk et al. 2021). The intentional influence is expressed through state and municipal policies targeting the development of the suburban zone or its specific parts, as exemplified by the intensified investments made by the Vinnytsia city administration into the transport and social infrastructure of the eastern section of the suburban area, which was incorporated into the Vinnytsia municipal territorial community.

Accordingly, what we observe is not merely suburbanisation but rather a multiplicity of suburbanisms and the gradual maturation of a holistic urban-rural continuum within the peri-urban area (Iaquinta and Drescher 2002; McGregor et al. 2005; Avram 2009; Piorr et al. 2011; Ravetz et al. 2013), where urban, suburban, and rural architectural forms, lifestyles, and land-use practices coexist, hybridise, and fluidly interact in varying proportions (Waugh 2000; Thuo 2013; Phelps 2017; Keil 2018; Ubarevičienė and Burneika 2020; Lozynskiy 2022). Importantly, the same factors may have different, sometimes even diametrically opposed effects depending on the processes and development aspects in question, the balance of which may shift over time even within the same suburban zone. For instance, a hilly landscape and high forest coverage – attributes valued by a classical suburbanite seeking a picturesque environment – may be irrelevant or even undesirable for a low-income migrant in search of affordable housing with good access to the city via public transportation, or for an entrepreneur looking for a location to establish a logistics hub or industrial facility.

Although the development of the peri-urban area—and suburbanisation in particular—entails numerous social, economic, and environmental challenges, including for second-tier post-socialist cities (Matlovič and Sedláková 2007; Slaev and Kovachev 2014; Kubeš and Nováček 2019; Lozynskiy 2019; Hardi et al. 2020; Ubarevičienė and Burneika 2020; Ilieva et al. 2023), these processes can and should be managed (Kubeš and Nováček 2019; Lozynskiy 2019; Cat-

tivelli 2021; Hardi 2022; Ilyniak 2024; Kazakov et al. 2024; Pavlov et al. 2024). Understanding the drivers that lead different parts of the peri-urban area to develop in distinct ways and identifying the spatial patterns that may emerge at different stages of development will enable urban planners to design more effective spatial development strategies for suburban spaces and their interaction with the central city (Lozynskyi 2019). Thus, scientists, local authorities, real-estate developers and the local population represent the principal beneficiaries of the current study's results.

5. Conclusions

The present research contributes to a relatively underrepresented body of literature on second-tier cities in Ukraine with regards to their suburban/peri-urban development. It advocates for greater attention to smaller urban centres, whose peri-urban transitions may differ markedly from those of larger metropolises yet are equally crucial for national spatial development strategies.

The suburban development of Vinnytsia demonstrates the spatial and functional complexity typical of post-socialist second-tier cities. Although suburbanisation – particularly residential and, to a lesser extent, commercial – plays a central role in reshaping the city's suburban area, this study reveals that the city's influence extends beyond mere population relocation. A nuanced blend of suburbanisation and broader modernisation processes is evident, manifesting in both spontaneous and policy-driven transformations.

The analysis of four key indicators—population growth, housing modernisation, real estate market activity, and construction permits—enabled the delineation of three concentric suburban zones with varying developmental dynamics. The dominant driver across all indicators is the proximity to the central city. Settlements located within 10 km of the city centre are most likely to experience intensive suburban development, consistent with the classical model of western-style suburbanisation. Beyond this range, housing modernisation becomes more prominent than new construction, reflecting a different set of motivations and capacities among residents. Additional factors influencing suburban development include proximity to highways, landscape aesthetics, and settlement size. While forest and water coverage showed limited statistical significance, hilly terrain and forested areas appear to attract wealthier suburban migrants. Conversely, the spatial configuration of Vinnytsia, particularly the industrial zones on its north-eastern fringe, contributes to spatial asymmetry in suburban growth. These dynamics underscore the importance of both natural and urban structural factors in shaping peri-urban development.

For urban planners and policymakers, the research underscores the need to reconcile administrative boundaries with actual patterns of urban influence and mobility. Strengthening inter-municipal cooperation mechanisms, enhancing data availability, and tailoring planning strategies to local socio-spatial realities are critical for promoting balanced development. The findings support the notion that suburban development in post-socialist settings diverges from western trajectories, displaying hybrid patterns marked by unregulated sprawl and selective modernisation. This hybridisation necessitates flexible and context-specific policy responses.

References

- Avram S (2009) The Position of Rural-Urban Fringe in the Framework of Human Settlement System. *Forum Geografic* 8(8): 138–145.
- Beauregard RA (2006) *When America Became Suburban*. University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis, 228 pp.
- Boateng EY, Abaye DA (2019) A Review of the Logistic Regression Model with Emphasis on Medical Research. *Journal of Data Analysis and Information Processing* 07(4): 190–207. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jdaip.2019.74012>
- Bogusz H, Winnicki S, Wójcik P (2024) What factors contribute to uneven suburbanisation? Predicting the number of migrants from Warsaw to its suburbs with machine learning. *The Annals of Regional Science* 72(4): 1353–1382. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00168-023-01245-y>
- Borén T, Gentile M (2007) Metropolitan processes in post-communist states: an introduction. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography* 89(2): 95–110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0467.2007.00242.x>
- Brade I, Smigiel C, Kovács Z (2009) Suburban Residential Development in Post-socialist Urban Regions: The Case of Moscow, Sofia, and Budapest. In: Kilper H (Ed) *German Annual of Spatial Research and Policy 2009*. German Annual of Spatial Research and Policy, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 79–104. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-03402-2_7
- Cattivelli V (2021) Planning peri-urban areas at regional level: The experience of Lombardy and Emilia-Romagna (Italy). *Land Use Policy* 103: 105282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105282>
- Cocheci R-M, Petrișor A-I (2023) Extended suburbanization and land cover dynamics in post-socialist metropolitan areas: Evidence from Romania. *disP – The Planning Review* 59(2): 88–102. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02513625.2023.2257490>
- Czaková G (2009) Development and formation suburban hinterland of the city of Nitra. *Geographia Cassoviensis* 3(2): 34–42.
- Dębińska E, Pałubska JA (2021) Influence of the Central City on the Location of Commercial Buildings in the Agglomeration. The Example of Krakow, Poland. *Journal of Applied Engineering Sciences* 11(1): 17–22. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jaes-2021-0003>
- Denysyk GI, Liubchenko VY, Hudzevych AV, Zhovnir LF, Zakharchenko VI, Kostiuk BN, Panasenko BD (2008) *Atlas Vinnytskoi Oblasti [Atlas of Vinnytsia Region]*. Vinnytsia, State Cartographic Factory, 19 pp.
- DOM.RIA (2025) *Perevirena neruhomisty na mapi [Verified real estate on the map]*. <https://dom.ria.com/> [Accessed on 10.03.2025]
- Dudek-Mańkowska S, Grochowski M, Sitnik K (2024) Changes in the Characteristics of Suburbanization in the Warsaw Metropolitan Area in the First Decades of the 21st Century. *Sustainability* 16(11): 4827. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16114827>
- Dymitrow M, Stenseke M (2016) Rural-Urban Blurring and the Subjectivity Within. *Rural Landscapes: Society, Environment, History* 3(1): 4, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.16993/rl.1>
- Fisher T (2003) Differentiation of Growth Processes in the Peri-urban Region: An Australian Case Study. *Urban Studies* 40(3): 551–565. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0042098032000053914>
- Ford T (1999) Understanding population growth in the peri-urban region. *International Journal of Population Geography* 5(4): 297–311. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1220\(199907/08\)5:4<297::AID-IJPG152>3.0.CO;2-O](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1220(199907/08)5:4<297::AID-IJPG152>3.0.CO;2-O)
- Forsyth A (2012) Defining Suburbs. *Journal of Planning Literature* 27(3): 270–281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0885412212448101>

- Friedmann J (1972) A general theory of polarized development. In: NM Hansen (Ed) *Growth Centers in Regional Economic Development*, The Free Press, New York, 82–107.
- Geyer HS, Kontuly T (1993) A Theoretical Foundation for the Concept of Differential Urbanization. *International Regional Science Review* 15(2): 157–177. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016001769301500202>
- Gierczak-Korzeniowska B (2020) Suburban Rail in the Podkarpackie Voivodeship as a Factor Stimulating the Development in the Region. *Transportation Overview – Przegląd Komunikacyjny* 2020(2): 28–36. https://doi.org/10.35117/A_ENG_20_02_03
- Gnatiuk O (2016) Dakhy z suchasnykh materialiv yak marker modernizatsijnoho vplyvu mista na prymis'ku zonu (pryklad Vinnytsi) [Roofs made of modern materials as a marker of the city's modernisation impact on the peri-urban area (case of Vinnytsia)]. *Chasopys Kartohrafiji* 16: 39–47.
- Gnatiuk O (2017) Demographic dimension of suburbanization in Ukraine in the light of urban development theories. *AUC GEOGRAPHICA* 52(2): 151–163. <https://doi.org/10.14712/23361980.2017.12>
- Gnatiuk O, Mezentsev K, Provotar N (2021) From the agricultural station to a luxury village? Changing and ambiguous everyday practices in the suburb of Vinnytsia (Ukraine). *Moravian Geographical Reports* 29(3): 202–216. <https://doi.org/10.2478/mgr-2021-0015>
- Golubchikov O, Makhrova A, Phelps N (2010) Post-socialist post-suburbia: growth machine and the emergence of “edge city” in the metropolitan context of Moscow. *Geography, Environment, Sustainability* 3(1): 44–55. <https://doi.org/10.24057/2071-9388-2010-3-1-44-55>
- Google Maps (2024) https://www.google.com/maps/@49.2283394,28.4661891,31.961m/data=!3m1!1e3?entry=tту&g_ep=EgoyMDI1MDkxNy4wIKXMDSoASAFQAw%3D%3D [Accessed on 25.10.2024].
- Gottero E, Larcher F, Cassatella C (2023) Defining and Regulating Peri-Urban Areas through a Landscape Planning Approach: The Case Study of Turin Metropolitan Area (Italy). *Land* 12(1): 217. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12010217>
- Hägerstrand T (1967) *Innovation Diffusion as a Spatial Process*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London, 350 pp.
- Halás M, Roubínek P, Kládvo P (2012) Urbánní a suburbánní prostor Olomouce: teoretické přístupy, vymezení, typologie. *Geografický časopis* 64(4): 289–310.
- Hardi T (2022) Differences and similarities in the expansion of suburban built-up areas around the different city regions of three Central European countries. *Tér és Társadalom* 36(3): 165–193. <https://doi.org/10.17649/TET.36.3.3429>
- Hardi T, Repaská G, Veselovský J, Viliňová K (2020) Environmental consequences of the urban sprawl in the suburban zone of Nitra: An analysis based on landcover data. *Geographica Pannonica* 24(3): 205–220. <https://doi.org/10.5937/gp24-25543>
- Harris R (2010) Meaningful types in a world of suburbs. In: Clapson M, Hutchison R (Eds) *Research in Urban Sociology*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 15–47. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S1047-0042\(2010\)0000010004](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1047-0042(2010)0000010004)
- Havryliuk O (2021) Differential and non-differential urbanization in Ukraine during the soviet and post-soviet era. *Visnyk of V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, series Geography. Ecology* (55): 141–158. <https://doi.org/10.26565/2410-7360-2021-55-11>
- Havryliuk O (2024) Socio-Economic Challenges of Integration and Spatial Distribution of War-Induced Internally Displaced Persons. *Demography and social economy* (1): 114–132. <https://doi.org/10.15407/dse2024.01.114>

- Havryliuk O, Gnatiuk O, Mezentsev K (2021) Suburbanization, but centralization? Migration patterns in the post-Soviet functional urban region – evidence from Kyiv. *Folia Geographica* 63(1): 64–84.
- Hirt S (2007) Suburbanizing Sofia: Characteristics of Post-Socialist Peri-Urban Change. *Urban Geography* 28(8): 755–780. <https://doi.org/10.2747/0272-3638.28.8.755>
- Iaquinta DL, Drescher AW (2002) Defining the peri-urban: rural-urban linkages and institutional connections. *Land reform, land settlement and cooperatives* 2: 8–26 https://www.fao.org/4/x8050t/x8050t02.htm#P10_2282
- Ilieva N, Hardi T, Genchev S, Ravnachka A, Poleganova D, Rácz S, Kazakov B (2023) Suburbanization processes in second tier cities in Bulgaria – demographic, socio-economic, and spatial transformation of the agglomeration areas (a case study of Plovdiv and Burgas). *Problems of Geography* 1-2: 63–90. <https://doi.org/10.35101/prg-2023.1-2.5>
- Ilyniak S (2024) Decentralization in Ukraine: Reorganizing Core–Periphery Relations? *Urban Planning* 9: 7642. <https://doi.org/10.17645/up.7642>
- Jurkowski W, Kryczka P, Figlus T, Lisowska-Kierepka A, Musiaka Ł, Sikorski D, Spórna T, Sudra P, Szmytkie R (2024) Long-term impact of railway transport on morphological development of the largest urban agglomerations in Poland. *Moravian Geographical Reports* 32(4): 245–257. <https://doi.org/10.2478/mgr-2024-0020>
- Boris K, Hardi T, Nadezhda I, Aleksandra R, Rácz S, Smahó M (2024) Suburbanization Processes in Sofia: Demographic, Socio-Economic and Spatial Transformation of the Agglomeration Area. *Tér és Társadalom* 38(1): 32–55. <https://doi.org/10.17649/TET.38.1.3541>
- Keil R (2018) *Suburban Planet: Making the World Urban from the Outside* in. *Urban Future Series*. Polity Press, Cambridge, 256 pp.
- Kok H, Kovács Z (1999) The process of suburbanization in the agglomeration of Budapest. *Netherlands Journal of Housing and the Built Environment* 14(2): 119–141. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02496818>
- Kontuly T, Geyer HS (2003) Lessons Learned from Testing the Differential Urbanisation Model. *Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie* 94(1): 124–128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9663.00242>
- Kryczka P, Sikorski D, Figlus T, Lisowska-Kierepka A, Musiaka Ł, Spórna T, Sudra P, Szmytkie R (2025) Defining suburbanization in Central and Eastern Europe: A systematic literature review. *Cities* 158: 105626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2024.105626>
- Kubeš J, Nováček A (2019) Suburbs around the Czech provincial city of České Budějovice – territorial arrangement and problems. *Hungarian Geographical Bulletin* 68(1): 65–78. <https://doi.org/10.15201/hungeobull.68.1.5>
- Kubeš J, Ouředníček M (2022) Functional types of suburban settlements around two differently sized Czech cities. *Cities* 127: 103742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2022.103742>
- Leetmaa K, Tammaru T (2007) Suburbanization in countries in transition: destinations of suburbanizers in the urban metropolitan area. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography* 89(2): 127–146. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0467.2007.00244.x>
- Leetmaa K, Tammaru T, Anniste K (2009) From priority-led to market-led urbanization in a post-communist metropolis. *Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie* 100(4): 436–453. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9663.2009.00551.x>
- Leetmaa K, Brade I, Anniste K, Nuga M (2012) Socialist Summer-home Settlements in Post-socialist Suburbanisation. *Urban Studies* 49(1): 3–21. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098010397399>

- Lozynskiy R (2019) Rethinking the role of land privatization in peri-urban transformations in Ukraine: The case study of Sokilnyky, Lviv oblast. *Human Geography Journal* 27: 48–59. <https://doi.org/10.26565/2076-1333-2019-27-06>
- Lozynskiy R (2022) Suburb as a socio-spatial phenomenon and post-socialist city. *Human Geography Journal* 32: 24–33. <https://doi.org/10.26565/2076-1333-2022-32-03>
- Main Department of Statistics in Vinnytsia Region (2025) Golovne upravlinnya statistiki u vinnitsykyi oblasti [Main Department of Statistics in Vinnytsia Region]. <https://www.vn.ukrstat.gov.ua/> [Accessed on 18.11.2024].
- Malchykova D, Pylypenko I (2017) Vid "rozirvanogo" prostoru do metropolizatsii i suburbanizatsii: Hersonsyka misyka aglomeratsiya u novih vimirah urbogenezu [From "torn" space to metropolitanisation and suburbanisation: Kherson urban agglomeration in new dimensions of urbogenesis]. In: K Mezentsev, Y Oliynyk, N Mezentseva (Eds) *Urban Ukraine: In the Epicentre of Spatial Changes*, Fenix, Kyiv, 327–339.
- Mantey D, Sudra P (2019) Types of suburbs in post-socialist Poland and their potential for creating public spaces. *Cities* 88: 209–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2018.11.001>
- Marcińczak S (2012) The evolution of spatial patterns of residential segregation in Central European Cities: The Łódź Functional Urban Region from mature socialism to mature post-socialism. *Cities* 29(5): 300–309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2011.08.008>
- Marushchynets A (2020) Defining Boundaries and Dynamics of Urbanized Areas According to Remote Data Sensing. *Ekonomichna ta Sotsialna Geografiya* 83: 46–52. <https://doi.org/10.17721/2413-7154/2020.83.46-52>
- Matlovič R, Sedláková A (2007) The impact of suburbanisation in the hinterland of Prešov (Slovakia). *Moravian Geographical Reports* 15(2): 22–31.
- McGregor D, Simon D, Thompson D (2005). *The Peri-Urban Interface. Approaches to Sustainable Natural and Human Resource Use*. Earthscan, London, Sterling VA 306 pp.
- Mezentsev K (2017) Vstup: zmina misykoï merezhi Ukraïni. [Introduction: Changing and emerging suburban areas.] In: K Mezentsev, Y Oliynyk, N Mezentseva (Eds) *Urban Ukraine: In the Epicentre of Spatial Changes*, Kyiv, Fenix, 261–267.
- Mezentsev K, Havryliuk O (2015) Testing of the differential urbanization model in Ukraine. *Ekonomichna ta Sotsialna Geografiya* 73(3): 15–26. <https://doi.org/10.17721/2413-7154/2015.73.15-26>
- Mezentsev K, Mezentseva N (2017) Zhitlova suburbanizatsiya v Ukraïni: trendi ta vidminnosti [Residential suburbanization in Ukraine: trends and differences]. In: K Mezentsev, Y Oliynyk, N Mezentseva (Eds) *Urban Ukraine: In the Epicentre of Spatial Changes*, Kyiv, Fenix, 268–287.
- Mezentsev K, Provotar N, Gnatiuk O, Melnychuk A, Denysenko O (2019) Ambiguous suburban spaces: trends and features of changing every-day practices. *Ekonomichna ta Sotsialna Geografiya* 82: 4–19. <https://doi.org/10.17721/2413-7154/2019.82.4-19>
- Mezentsev K, Provotar N, Gnatiuk O, Melnychuk A, Denysenko O (2020) Development trajectories of suburban spaces. *Scientific Bulletin of Kherson State University – Geographical Sciences* 13: 63–75. <https://doi.org/10.32999/ksu2413-7391/2020-13-7>
- Official Register of Planning Conditions and Restrictions (2025) https://e-construction.gov.ua/mist_bud_cr [Accessed on 14.02.2025].
- Osada S (2003) The Japanese urban system 1970–1990. *Progress in Planning* 59(3): 125–231. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-9006\(02\)00111-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-9006(02)00111-3)
- Ouředníček M (2007) Differential suburban development in the Prague urban region. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography* 89(2): 111–126. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0467.2007.00243.x>

- Pavlov O, Pavlova I, Pavlov O, Didukh S, Lagodiienko V (2024) Inclusive Development of Rural-Urban Agglomerations of Ukraine: Capacity, Sectoral and Socio-Economic Orientation, Trends. *European Countryside* 16(2): 337–359. <https://doi.org/10.2478/euco-2024-0019>
- Peduzzi P, Concato J, Kemper E, Holford TR, Feinstein AR (1996) A simulation study of the number of events per variable in logistic regression analysis. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 49(12): 1373–1379. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0895-4356\(96\)00236-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0895-4356(96)00236-3)
- Peiffer-Smadja O, Torre A (2018) Retail decentralization and land use regulation policies in suburban and rural communities: The case of the Île-de-France region. *Habitat International* 72: 27–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2017.02.003>
- Perroux F (1955). Note sur la notion de pôle de croissance. *Économie Appliquée*, 8(1): 307–320.
- Pidgrushnyi GP, Mezentsev KV, Dudin VS, Provotar NI, Bondar VV (2020) Commercial suburbanization in Kyiv metropolitan region: uneven development and polycentricity. *Ukrainian Geographical Journal* 4: 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.15407/ugz2020.04.019>
- Pidgrushnyi GP, Provotar NI, Dudin VS (2023) Spatial Characteristics of the Kyiv Metropolitan Region Development: the Dimensions of Polycentricity. *Ukrainian Geographical Journal* 1: 23–34. <https://doi.org/10.15407/ugz2023.01.023>
- Pierr A, Ravetz J, Tosics I (2011) Peri-Urbanisation in Europe. Towards European Policies to Sustain Urban-Rural Futures. Synthesis Report, 148 pp.
- Phelps NA (2017) 1. Introduction: Old Europe: New suburbanization? In: NA Phelps (Ed) *Old Europe: New Suburbanization. Governance, Land and Infrastructure in European Suburbanization*, Toronto, University of Toronto Press, 3–17. <https://doi.org/10.3138/9781442616479-004>
- Podawca K, Karsznia K, Zawrzykraj AP (2019) The assessment of the suburbanisation degree of Warsaw Functional Area using changes of the land development structure. *Miscellanea Geographica* 23(4): 215–224. <https://doi.org/10.2478/mgrsd-2019-0019>
- Population Statistic of Eastern Europe (2024) All places: 1989, 2001 census (present population). <http://pop-stat.mashke.org/ukraine-census-pres/total.htm> [Accessed on 18.11.2024].
- Provotar N, Melnychuk V (2025) Diversity of suburban spaces: The case of rural street in Kyiv's changing suburbia. *Czasopismo Geograficzne* 96(1): 175–199. <https://doi.org/10.12657/czageo-96-08>
- Ravetz J, Fertner C, Nielsen TS (2013) The Dynamics of Peri-Urbanization. In: Nilsson K, Pauleit S, Bell S, Aalbers C, Sick Nielsen TA (Eds) *Peri-urban futures: Scenarios and models for land use change in Europe*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 13–44. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-30529-0_2
- Repaská G, Vilinová K, Šolcová L (2017) Trends in Development of Residential Areas in Suburban Zone of the City of Nitra (Slovakia). *European Countryside* 9(2): 287–301. <https://doi.org/10.1515/euco-2017-0018>
- Ronse W, Boussauw K, Lauwers D (2015) Shopping Centre Siting and Modal Choice in Belgium: A Destination-Based Analysis. *European Planning Studies* 23(11): 2275–2291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2014.965132>
- Sikorski D, Szmytkie R (2021) Changes in the distribution of economic activity in Wrocław and its suburban area, 2008–2016. *Bulletin of Geography. Socio-economic Series* 54: 33–48. <https://doi.org/10.2478/bog-2021-0031>
- Slaev AD, Kovachev A (2015) Specific Issues of Urban Sprawl in Bulgaria. *European Spatial Research and Policy* 21(2): 155–169. <https://doi.org/10.1515/esrp-2015-0010>

- Sýkora L, Posová D (2011). Formy urbanizace: kritické zhodnocení modelu stadií vývoje měst a návrh alternativní metody klasifikace forem urbanizace. *Geografie* 116(1): 1–22.
- Šveda M, Madajová M, Podolák P (2016) Behind the Differentiation of Suburban Development in the Hinterland of Bratislava, Slovakia. *Czech Sociological Review* 52(6): 893–926. <https://doi.org/10.13060/00380288.2016.52.6.290>
- Sýkora L, Ouředníček M (2007) Sprawling Post-Communist Metropolis: Commercial and Residential Suburbanization in Prague and Brno, the Czech Republic. In: E Razin, M Dijkstra, C. Vázquez (Eds) *Employment Deconcentration in European Metropolitan Areas*, Dordrecht, Springer, 209–233. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-5762-5_8
- Tanaš J (2013) Differentiation of Local Housing Markets in the Poznań Suburban Area. *Real Estate Management and Valuation* 21(3): 88–98. <https://doi.org/10.2478/remav-2013-0030>
- Thuo ADM (2013) Unsettled settled spaces: Searching for a theoretical ‘home’ for rural-urban fringes. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications* 3(7): 1–17.
- Ubarevičienė R, Burneika D, Van Ham M (2015) Ethno-Political Effects of Suburbanization in the Vilnius Urban Region: An Analysis of Voting Behavior. *Journal of Baltic Studies* 46(2): 217–242. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01629778.2015.1027935>
- Ubarevičienė R, Burneika D (2020) Fast and uncoordinated suburbanization of Vilnius in the context of depopulation in Lithuania. *Environmental & Socio-economic Studies* 8(4): 44–56. <https://doi.org/10.2478/environ-2020-0022>
- Udovychenko V, Melnychuk A, Gnatiuk O, Ostapenko P (2017) Decentralization Reform in Ukraine: Assessment of the Chosen Transformation Model. *European Spatial Research and Policy* 24(1): 23–40. <https://doi.org/10.1515/esrp-2017-0002>
- Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (2024) On administrative and territorial structure of Ukraine (Law of Ukraine No. 3285-IX, adopted on 24 May 2024). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/3285-20#Text> [Accessed on 23.02.2025].
- Vinnytsia City Council (2021) Vinnytsia Master Plan. <https://2021.vmr.gov.ua/Branches/Lists/ArchitectureAndCityBuilding/ShowContent.aspx?ID=1> [Accessed on 10.03.2025]
- Vittinghoff E, McCulloch CE (2007) Relaxing the Rule of Ten Events per Variable in Logistic and Cox Regression. *American Journal of Epidemiology* 165(6): 710–718. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwk052>
- Walks A (2013) Suburbanism as a Way of Life, Slight Return. *Urban Studies* 50(8): 1471–1488. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098012462610>
- Waugh D (2000) *Geography. An Integrated Approach*. Nelson Thornes, 656 pp.
- Werner PA, Kaleyeva V, Porczek M (2022) Urban Sprawl in Poland (2016–2021): Drivers, Wildcards, and Spatial Externalities. *Remote Sensing* 14(12): 2804. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14122804>
- Wolny A, Żróbek R (2017) The interdependence between suburban enclaves and the road network in the development process: A case study in Poland. *Geographia Polonica* 90(2): 41–57. <https://doi.org/10.7163/GPol.0086>
- Zakutynska I, Slyvka R (2016) *Suburbanizatsiya v prostorovomu vimiri: Ivano-Fran-kivsyk i yogo okolitsi* [Suburbanisation in the Spatial Dimension: Ivano-Frankivsk and its Surroundings]. Lohos, Kyiv, 215 pp.
- Zębik G (2011) Typology of Suburban Communities in Poland. *Bulletin of Geography. Socio-economic Series* 16: 173–188. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10089-011-0021-x>
- Zborowski A, Gałka J, Surmacz-Wybrańczyk M (2023) How are suburbanization and peri-urbanization not the same? Key differences in urban regions in Central and Eastern European countries: the case of cities in southern Poland. *Bulletin of Geography. Socio-economic Series* 62: 87–106. <https://doi.org/10.12775/bgss-2023-0036>

Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: OG. Data curation: OG. Investigation: OG. Methodology: OG. Visualization: AK. Writing - original draft: OG, AK.

Author ORCIDs

Oleksiy Gnatiuk <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1818-2415>

Anna Klymenko <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9571-8661>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

Supplementary material 1

Datasheet

Authors: Oleksiy Gnatiuk

Data type: Datasheet

Explanation note: A Table in MS Excel format containing the raw data per suburban settlement for analysis.

Copyright notice: This dataset is made available under the Open Database License (<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0/>). The Open Database License (ODbL) is a license agreement intended to allow users to freely share, modify, and use this Dataset while maintaining this same freedom for others, provided that the original source and author(s) are credited.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/jbgs.e157082.suppl1>